

TWENTY-THIRD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

3D Printed Continuous Fiber Reinforced Composites of Anisotropic Topology Optimized Structures

Yiming Huang

PhD Candidate

Supervised by Prof Xiaoyong Tian

State Key Laboratory for Manufacturing System Engineering

Xi'an Jiaotong University

Contents

Research Background

Materials and Methods

Experimental Verification

Summary

1. Research Background

■ Wide-Ranging Application of Fiber Reinforced Composites

- High specific strength
- High specific modulus
- Design flexibility, ...

Vehicle Body of the BMW 7 SERIES

Sources: www.airliners.de

1. Research Background

■ Manufacturing Process of Continuous Fiber Reinforced Composites (CFRCs)

3D printing path

➤ More complex structure can be realized

**Topology
optimized
structures**

Additive Manufacturing 38 (2021) 101842

1. Research Background

■ Topology Optimization of CFRCs

Additive Manufacturing 44 (2021) 102056

Composites Science and Technology 204 (2021) 108644

Composites Science and Technology 230 (2022) 109727

Anisotropic property

Path planning

Performance

Contents

Research Background

Materials and Methods

Experimental Verification

Summary

2. Materials and Methods

■ Multidisciplinary framework to design and produce a topology optimized structure

2. Materials and Methods

Equipment and material

3D printer

Shaanxi Fibertech Technology Development Co., Ltd.

V_F (%)	E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	ν_{xy}
6.67	12.3331	1.7557	0.9880	0.3673
10	15.0108	1.7818	1.0071	0.3660
15	19.0340	1.7762	1.0370	0.3640
20	23.0571	1.7170	1.0689	0.3620
25	27.0803	1.6041	1.1027	0.3600
30	31.1034	1.4376	1.1388	0.3580
35	35.1266	1.2175	1.1772	0.3560
40	39.1497	0.9438	1.2184	0.3540

2. Materials and Methods

■ Topology optimization

$$\min : c(\rho, \theta) = U(\rho, \theta)^T F$$

$$\text{s.t.} \begin{cases} \frac{V(x)}{V_0} = f \\ KU = F \\ 0 < \rho_{\min} \leq \rho \leq 1 \\ -2\pi \leq \theta \leq 2\pi \end{cases}$$

Optimization result

- Constant fiber content ($V_f = 10\%$)

3D printing path in local areas

$$g_i = \frac{1}{\sum_{e=1}^{n_e} \rho_e} \sum_{e=1}^{n_e} \rho_e \theta_e$$

Simultaneous optimal designs for both **material distribution** and **fiber orientation**

2. Materials and Methods

■ Path Planning

Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm (MBB) Beam

Shape topology

Printing path

Topology optimized structures can be produced by this continuous printing path

2. Materials and Methods

■ Progressive design of fiber content

Contents

Research Background

Materials and Methods

Experimental Verification

Summary

3. Experimental Verification

■ 3D printed topology optimized structures of two benchmark geometries

3. Experimental Verification

■ Cantilever beam

Universal testing machine (PLD-5kN, LETRY Corp., China)

- **123.07 % in structural stiffness increase**
- **52.16 % in peak load increase**

3. Experimental Verification

■ MBB beam

- **36.27 % in structural stiffness increase**
- **64.43 % in peak load increase**

- Structural stiffness: **541.77 N/mm**
- Peak load: **1406.44 N**

3. Experimental Verification

■ MBB beam with different fiber contents

120*40*10 mm

3. Experimental Verification

■ MBB beam with different fiber contents

3. Experimental Verification

■ MBB beam with different fiber contents

Inhomogeneous distributions of fiber content can further improve performance

Contents

Research Background

Materials and Methods

Experimental Verification

Summary

4. Summary

- ◆ **Topology optimization and 3D printing could promote the potential of CFRCs, and even challenge traditional design and manufacturing mechanism relating material and structure scale.**

Acknowledgement

National Key R&D Program of China (2018YFE0207900)

National Natural Science Foundation of China (52075422)

K C Wong Education Foundation

The Youth Innovation Team of Shaanxi Universities

Thank you for your attention !

Yiming Huang

State Key Laboratory for Manufacturing System Engineering

Xi'an Jiaotong University

Email: *hyming0721@163.com*